

**LITERATURE AND JOURNALISM IN A NOVEL
BASED ON A REAL-LIFE MURDER CASE - TRUMAN
CAPOTE'S 'IN COLD BLOOD'**

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Abstract: *In Cold Blood* is widely considered one of the first and the most significant literary works in the true crime genre. Numerous subsequent similar works were influenced by Truman Capote's rigorous research, as well as his vivid, authentic style which established a benchmark for non-fiction crime literature. The distinctive fusion of journalistic and literary components included in this novel created the premises for a huge impact on the true crime genre, establishing a firm standard for the authentic, emotional narrative and the in-depth examination of true criminal cases. Truman Capote's approach and the style he flaunted in *In Cold Blood* are undoubtedly a testament to the effectiveness of narrative nonfiction, fusing literary attributes with journalistic techniques in order to produce a compelling and provocative depiction of a heinous multiple murder.

Key words: Truman Capote, authenticity, nonfiction, true crime, literature, journalism

Truman Capote (born Truman Streckfus Persons) was an American novelist, playwright, and short-story writer. He was born in New Orleans, Louisiana, on September 30, 1924, and died in Los Angeles, California, on August 25, 1984. His early literary works were rooted in the Southern Gothic tradition, but he later adopted a more journalistic style in his novel *In Cold Blood* (1966), which, along with *Breakfast at Tiffany's* (1958), is still his best-known work⁷.

Capote had a growing interest in journalism that became evident in his nonfiction book *In Cold Blood*, which tells the harrowing story of the 1959 brutal murder of the four members of the Clutter family (Herb, his wife, Bonnie, and their teenage children Nancy and Kenyon) from Holcomb, a peaceful town in Kansas. Soon after the murders took place,

⁷ <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Truman-Capote>

Capote started investigating them, and he spent six years interviewing the two men who were ultimately sentenced to death for that crime and executed on April 14, 1965. Truman Capote lived in Kansas (in Garden City, actually, a town near Holcomb) for several months with the "assistant researchist" Harper Lee, his childhood friend and fellow novelist. The book was released in 1966 after a four-part series was published in *The New Yorker* in 1965. It was the pinnacle of Capote's careers as a writer and a journalist, catapulting him to the forefront of the then-emerging New Journalism thanks to the critical and popular acclaim of the novel⁸.

Photo: www.thefirstedition.com

Truman Capote's *In Cold Blood* is obviously an innovative work that blurs the line between literature and journalism and which is considered one of the earliest and most influential examples of the true crime genre, a non-fiction novel. Capote's research and writing efforts coincided with the rise of the so-called New Journalism which was

⁸ Ibid.

established by Norman Mailer, amongst some other authors: "As it happens, Capote and Mailer were exact contemporaries and published their first novels - *The Naked and the Dead* and *Other Voices, Other Rooms* - in 1948, in each case mostly to acclaim"⁹. The approach Truman Capote uses in order to write *In Cold Blood* incorporates both literary and journalistic elements, which contributes to the the impact and the lasting legacy of the book. Capote's unique authorial perspective, based on authenticity, challenged the boundaries between fiction and non-fiction. He creatively pioneered a genre known as narrative nonfiction, creative nonfiction, or literary nonfiction, combining the factual accuracy of journalism with literary techniques and the emotional depth of fiction. Consequently, *In Cold Blood* has had a profound impact on both the literary and journalistic fields and influenced subsequent true crime authors, journalists, and creative non-fiction writers, as it continues to be studied in literature and journalism courses all over the world.

Perry Smith and Richard Hickock, the two murderers, as well as the Clutter family members, are all skillfully portrayed by the journalist-writer. Truman Capote explores their backgrounds, psychology, and motivations, making them complex and, ultimately, human. This character construction goes beyond traditional journalism and it is more akin to the depth reached in a literary work. Capote uses a storytelling style that appeals to the emotions of the readers as much as their intellect. He makes the audience feel sympathetic towards the victims and unsettlingly fascinated by the killers. With its rich imagery and intricate details, the book works like a proper novel even though Capote uses cinematographic techniques and makes his literary work have the nature of a documentary, as emphasized by Robert Emmet Long, who also stresses that the style remains similar to Capote's early gothic stories: "Although sometimes held in abeyance, Gothicism never entirely disappeared from his writing, and *with In Cold Blood* this element reappears powerfully, in a new form in a work remarkable for the breadth of its exacting realism. Gothicism has as one of its foremost components an element of fantasy, but *In Cold Blood* that fantasy has

⁹ Robert Emmet Long, *Truman Capote – Enfant Terrible*, p.81, The Continuum International Publishing Group Inc, New York, 2008

been socialized by being 'true' (...) Gothicism in the novel is also hinted at in the initial account of the Clutter murders by the fact that the murderer had placed a pillow under his victims' heads before shooting them in the face with a shotgun. Capote is a master at noting details that leap out at the reader. Hickock's left eye is called 'serpentine' and seems to 'warn of bitter sediment at the bottom of his nature'"¹⁰.

Truman Capote spent years gathering information on the case through in-depth investigations and interviews. He talked to the killers extensively, as well as to law enforcement officials and members of the community. The writer visited Holcomb, Kansas, in 1959, after reading in the New York Times about the murders of the four members of the Clutter family in their rural, idyllic environment. Capote was accompanied by two friends, fellow novelist Harper Lee and New Yorker fact-checker Sandy M. Campbell. His goal was to explore the case, interview Holcomb's investigators and others, and write about the crime and inquiry. *In Cold Blood* was originally published as a four-part series in The New Yorker magazine in 1965 and was described as a "nonfiction novel." Although Capote followed the novel-writing conventions, he claimed that his work was completely truthful, and the quotes came directly from his interviews. Nevertheless, many have questioned the reality of Capote's work and his use of creative license to imagine unknowable details. The involvement of the writer with law enforcement officials and with the men ultimately convicted of the crime may have colored the stories they shared with him, as some speculate¹¹.

But this meticulous investigative work is nevertheless a hallmark of journalism. In an effort to maintain his objectivity, Capote presents the case's facts and the trial's proceedings without directly expressing his opinions. He leaves it up to the reader to make their own judgments on the information he provides. But the plenary involvement in the story and its development would take its toll on Truman Capote from a psychological point of view, as William Todd Schultz writes: "In some ways, Capote never really got home. A bit of Kansas, and Smith, stayed

¹⁰ Robert Emmet Long, *Truman Capote – Enfant Terrible*, pp.89-90, The Continuum International Publishing Group Inc, New York, 2008

¹¹ *In Cold Blood: Truman Capote in Holcomb, Kansas*, <https://beineckerroadshow.yale.edu/cold-blood-truman-capote-holcomb-kansas>

in him forever. He came to understand, he said, that death is the “central factor” of life. That simple comprehension altered his entire perspective. *In Cold Blood* was a turning point, a climactic moment. It was ‘the most emotional experience’ of his creative life. But the darkened hallway he now found himself in was about to get inestimably darker. In his moment of unraveling, of losing his grip, he did the opposite of lying low. He upped the ante. He rolled loaded dice”¹².

Capote was so concerned about the psychological roots of the horrendous crime and its perpetrators to the extent that he was willing to contest the ways in which the court dealt with this issue: “The medical evidence came from two sources: court-appointed generalists from the local community and a keen, young, forensic psychiatrist from out of town. All came to the same conclusion on the single dichotomous question asked of them, rooted in the rigidly cognitive M’Naghton rules: the killers did indeed know right from wrong. But Capote is clear that the forensic psychiatrist wanted to say more, to give an explanation in mitigation for Smith, who had had such a traumatic life. The court allowed him no opportunity to do so. (...) Underlying these courtroom politics are more fundamental questions about the nature of criminal responsibility and mitigation. For Capote, Smith was less culpable because he was understandable. Hickock was born bad, presumably through no fault of his own, yet is regarded as more deserving of punishment. Why should mitigation depend on our ability to understand? And when psychiatry has explained the truth about the criminal, rather than the crime, what then for justice?”¹³.

Truman Capote's in-depth characterization of the victims and the killers, Perry Smith and Richard "Dick" Hickock, humanized the individuals involved in this case. This aspect gave the narrative another level of complexity and depth and helped readers comprehend the emotional and psychological states of the characters. But reading it, and especially rereading it, is a disturbing experience for most, including Harold Bloom, who doesn't question the authenticity of Truman

¹² William Todd Schultz, *Tiny Terror. Why Truman Capote (Almost) Wrote Answered Prayers*, p.99, Oxford University Press, 2011

¹³ Thomas Clarke, ‘*In Cold Blood*’ by Truman Capote, *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 209, p. 191, doi: 10.1192/bjpp.116.182568

Capote's literary and journalistic endeavour and who considers that *In Cold Blood* is still the most effective nonfiction novel ever written: "I reread *In Cold Blood* rarely and reluctantly, because it is both depressing and rhetorically very effective. The depression, as rereading makes clear, is caused by Capote's covert imaginative identification with the murderers, Perry Smith and Richard Hickock. Perry Smith is Capote's *daemon* or other self, and it is no surprise to learn that Capote cultivated the murderers, wept for them at the scaffold, and paid for their burials. Whether the cold, artful book deserves canonical status, I am uncertain, but it is likely enough to survive. It reflects its America, which is still our own"¹⁴.

In conclusion, *In Cold Blood* is still regarded as a classic in the fields of journalism and literature. The novel pushes the frontiers of storytelling and non-fiction, challenging conventions and launching the genre of creative nonfiction. As one of the most significant works of American literature, *In Cold Blood* never fails to enthrall readers and inspire writers with its compelling narrative style, nuanced characterizations, complicated ethical issues, and enduring influence. Truman Capote's literary work is a proof of the narrative nonfiction's potency and the lasting legacy of a writer who dared to blur the lines between fact and fiction.

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¹⁴ Harold Bloom, *Introduction to Truman Capote - New Edition*, Edited and with an introduction by Harold Bloom, Sterling Professor of the Humanities, Yale University, p.2, Bloom's Literary Criticism, An imprint of Infobase Publishing, 2009

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